

Placement and acidification of biowastes: Potential strategies for improving phosphorus use efficiency

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to improve the phosphorus (P) use efficiency of various biowastes. To achieve this, we proposed the combination of placement and the acidification of biowastes for the development of P-efficient biobased fertilizers. Seven biowastes were used as P-fertilizers, including two meat and bone meals (MBM), two solid fractions of biogas digestate (BGF), and three sewage sludges (SS). Two acidification approaches were evaluated: pre-treatment with sulfuric acid (73.5 g sulfuric acid per kg fresh weight) and co-application with ammonium sulfate (15 mg N per kg soil). The treated materials were placed close to winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* cv. Benchmark) seeds in a 42-day pot experiment in a growth chamber. The P use efficiency was compared to the corresponding untreated material homogeneously mixed or similarly placed in the soil. A ³³P indirect labeling method was used to differentiate P uptake from soil and fertilizer. The negative control showed a shoot dry matter of 0.42 g (\pm 0.05) and a total P uptake of 0.62 (\pm 0.06) mg per plant. The placement of acidified sewage sludge did not show significant differences in shoot dry matter and P uptake compared to the negative control. On the other hand, the placement of acidified MBM significantly increased plant growth (MBM I: 2.93 \pm 0.46; MBM II: 1.78 \pm 0.09 g) and P uptake (MBM I: 7.38 \pm 1.10; MBM II: 6.21 \pm 0.53 mg) compared to the untreated MBM placed and the negative control. Similarly, the placement of acidified BGF showed promising results, with a 3-fold increase in P uptake from the fertilizer compared to untreated BGF mixed with the soil (7.74 \pm 1.47 vs. 2.71 \pm 0.26 mg). Therefore, our results demonstrate that the placement of acidified MBM and BGF can increase the P use efficiency of these biowastes and may provide a basis for formulating P-efficient biobased fertilizers using these materials.

1. Introduction

Biowastes can be an alternative to replace mineral phosphorus fertilizers in agriculture. Animal manure (20–30 Mt of P per year) and sewage sludge (3–5 Mt of P per year) are the two most important biowastes in the phosphorus flows within the European Union. In addition, a significant amount of phosphorus ends up in animal bones in slaughterhouses and can be applied to agricultural soils as meat and bone meal (0.1–1 Mt of P per year) (van Dijk et al., 2016). However, the P availability of these biowastes varies greatly and is often considerably lower than that of mineral fertilizers (Möller et al., 2018).

Meat and bone meal consists mainly of dried and ground residues of meat, blood, and bones. As a result, it has high carbon, calcium,

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and nitrogen contents, with phosphorus originating mainly from the bones in the form of hydroxyapatite (calcium-bound P) (Christiansen et al., 2020; Jeng et al., 2007; Kivelä et al., 2015). Consequently, meat and bone meal usually has a low fertilizer use efficiency compared to mineral fertilizers, ranging from 17 to 37% (Christiansen et al., 2020).

The separation of solid and liquid fractions of digestate is a process aimed at reducing nutrient losses to the environment and optimizing nutrient recycling, as in this process, most of the nitrogen is recovered in the liquid fraction (Tambone et al., 2017). During anaerobic digestion of animal manure, soluble phosphorus can precipitate with calcium, magnesium, or in the form of vivianite (iron-bound P) (Möller and Müller, 2012), which can be recovered in the solid fraction of the digestate (Chuda et al., 2021).

In wastewater treatment plants, iron and aluminum salts are used to precipitate phosphorus from sewage sludge. Treatment processes vary widely between plants, and the type and amount of salts strongly influence the P solubility and availability of the sewage sludge (Øgaard and Brod, 2016). Consequently, the average P efficiency of sewage sludge is usually below 60% compared to mineral fertilizers (Möller et al., 2018).

Based on this background, different approaches to increase the P use efficiency of biowastes merit research. The placement of fertilizers close to the seeds reduces the contact area between phosphorus and the soil, thereby minimizing its sorption by the soil (Grant et al., 2001). In addition, studies have shown that the placement of mineral fertilizers can result in higher amounts of P available to the crop during early growth stages, promoting plant growth and root proliferation in both the placement zone and the bulk soil (Lemming et al., 2016; van der Bom et al., 2023). This application method has also been shown to increase crop yields compared to the broadcast mineral fertilizer application (Cooke, 1954, 1949; Widdowson and Cooke, 1958).

However, the placement of biowastes may not have the same positive effects as observed with mineral fertilizers. Lemming et al. (2016) found that the placement of sewage sludge significantly reduced total P uptake compared to the mixed treatment. The authors suggested that the placement zone of biowastes has sufficient available P to induce root proliferation; however, this amount of available P is not enough to sustain plant growth. This implies an opportunity cost to the plant between proliferating root growth in the placement zone and exploring resources in the bulk soil, which negatively affects plant growth.

Different treatments have been proposed, aiming to increase the P solubility and availability of different biowastes. Wang et al. (2016) suggested that the co-localized application of sewage sludge with an ammonium source would cause an in-situ acidification effect in the placement zone, reducing the pH and solubilizing P. Amin (2023) co-applied bone char with different N sources, and found that the co-application with ammonium sulfate reduced soil pH and increased Ca and P solubility. Another promising approach to increase the soluble P fraction in biowastes is the pre-treatment with acids. Acidification of meat and bone meal and also of its derived biochar can increase its P solubility and availability Sica et al. (2023), Amin and Mihoub (2021); Zimmer et al. (2019)). Indeed, the acidification of meat and bone meal can increase its mineral fertilizer equivalent value from 17% to 74% (Damaceno et al., 2019). Sica et al. (2023) found that acidification can increase the proportion of water-extractable P of the digestate solid fraction from 17% to more than 70% of the total P. In another study, Regueiro et al. (2020) found a significant increase in P uptake by maize when comparing acidified digestate solid fraction with the corresponding untreated material. Acidification of sewage sludge and its derived ashes and biochar has also demonstrated promising results on increasing the P solubility and availability (Keskinen et al., 2023; Kopp et al., 2023).

Sica et al. (2023) investigated the interactions between fertilizer placement and acidification and found that the acidification of

Table 1
The chemical composition of the biomaterials that were assessed in this study.

	BGF I	BGF II	MBM I	MBM II	SS-B	SS-V	SS-Min
B*	35.5	29.8	5.8	1.3	42.8	39.3	35
Cd* ‡	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.9	0.9	0.8
Cr* ‡	9.5	10	4	5.3	35.5	42.9	35.0
Cu* ‡	82	101	16	15	323	458	590
Mn*	489	249	27	22	271	880	356
Zn* ‡	414	349	159	148	1079	1238	929
Al*	1.4	1.8	0.3	0.6	10	11.4	12.7
Ca*	36.7	19.9	67	56.8	57.1	44.6	31.5
Fe*	7.1	9.6	1.7	0.7	52	65	53.3
K*	11.3	12.7	7.1	9	3.5	4.4	4
Mg*	17.4	7.8	1.6	1.6	5.1	4.9	3.5
Na*	4	2.9	6.3	5.7	1.5	3	1.4
P *	33.1	12	39.6	36.4	41.5	40.2	34.3
S*	9.8	9.3	7.7	7.6	19.9	22.1	8.4
N * *	26.5	19.6	98.4	101	39.8	38.2	29.4
C* *	340	418	428	426	308	286	217
C/N	16.0	26.7	5.44	5.26	9.67	9.37	9.23
Ca/P	1.11	1.66	1.69	1.56	1.38	1.18	0.92
(Fe + Al)/P	0.17	0.62	0.03	0.03	1	1.2	1.3

BGF = biogas fiber; MBM = meat and bone meal; SS = sewage sludge.

*Determined by ICP-OES after microwave digestion with HNO₃, H₂O₂ and HF.

* *C and N of dried samples were determined by Elemental Analyzer.

‡According to the Danish executive order for the agricultural use of waste, the limit for heavy metal contents in wastes to be applied in agriculture are: Cr: 100 mg/kg; Cu: 1000 mg/kg; Zn: 4000 mg/kg; and Cd: 0.8 mg/kg (Miljøstyrelsen, 2018).

meat and bone meal, digestate solid fraction, and sewage sludge with sulfuric acid significantly increased P solubility, the P release from the fertilizer to the soil, and soil water-extractable P when these acidified biowastes were placed in the soil. The authors concluded that the placement of acidified biowastes may be a promising approach to increase the P fertilizer value of biowastes.

However, to the best of our knowledge, it has not yet been investigated how the placement of acidified biowastes affects plant P uptake and growth. The placement of fertilizers creates a nutrient-rich zone in the soil, which stimulates and intensifies biogeochemical processes in the placement zone and its surrounding soil. This may not only facilitate the nutrient acquisition by the plant (Meyer et al., 2023, 2020; Sica et al., 2023), but can also have toxic effects, inhibiting plant and root growth (Pan et al., 2016; Pedersen et al., 2020; Sica et al., 2023).

For this reason, the objective of this study was to evaluate how the placement of seven different acidified biowastes affected the P uptake and wheat growth. We hypothesized that *acidification will increase the P solubility of the biowastes, resulting in greater amounts of P being available to the plant at early stages when placed, thereby increasing plant growth.*

For this purpose, we evaluated four treatments for each biowaste: 1) untreated form mixed; 2) untreated form placed; 3) acidified form placed; 4) untreated form co-applied with ammonium sulfate. Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) was grown for 42 days in 2-L pots. The soil was labelled with ^{33}P to discriminate between the P uptake derived from the soil and that derived from the fertilizer.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fertilizer materials

The chemical composition of the biowastes used in this study is presented in Table 1 and was determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) after microwave digestion with HNO_3 , H_2O_2 , and HF.

The solid fraction of biogas digestate (BGF I) was sampled at the Maabjerg Energy Center (Holstebro, Denmark). The substrate of this biogas plant consists of approximately 70% cattle manure, 20% pig slurry, 8–9% poultry litter and 1–2% of food waste. The separation of the liquid and solid fractions is done using a screw-press, followed by a decanting centrifuge, which results in a high separation efficiency and higher P contents (Chuda et al., 2021). Further information on substrate composition and processing can be found in Liu et al. (2019). The second solid fraction of biogas digestate (BGF II) was collected as pellets from Limfjordens Bioenergi (Morsø, Denmark) and is based exclusively on livestock manure, using only a screw press for the separation of the liquid and solid fractions.

The meat and bone meal I (MBM I) was collected from the Daka SecAnim plant (Hedensted, Denmark). This material is of animal origin, mainly from livestock farming and slaughterhouse waste. The meat and bone meal II (MBM II) is a commercial pelletized biobased fertilizer from Daka SecAmin (Øgro 10–3-1).

One sewage sludge material (SS-B) was collected from the BIOFOS wastewater treatment plant located in Avedøre, Greater Copenhagen, which combines biological and chemical (FeClSO_4) P removal. In this plant, the sewage sludge undergoes the following processes: mesophilic anaerobic digestion and dewatering. Additional information on SS-B and its treatment can be found in López-Rayó et al. (2016) and Lemming et al. (2016).

The second sewage sludge material (SS-V) was collected from the VandCenter Syd wastewater treatment plant near the city of Odense, Denmark. Its treatment includes precipitation with ferrous sulfate ($\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$) followed by biological treatment, anaerobic digestion, and dewatering. More detailed information on the SS-V treatment processes can be found in Wang et al. (2022).

The mineralized sewage sludge (SS-Min) was collected from the Tysinge Renseanlæg wastewater treatment plant in Tølløse, Denmark. In the treatment process, the sludge is dewatered and mineralized in reed beds under aerobic conditions. Additional information about this sludge mineralization treatment can be found in Brix (2017).

Two different mineral P fertilizers were used. In one treatment, monopotassium phosphate (KH_2PO_4) was dissolved in water and applied as a nutrient solution to the soil. The D-coder (Dc) is a slow-release mineral fertilizer marketed by TimacAgro. More information on the formulation of this product can be found in Erro et al. (2007).

2.1.1. Acidification treatments

All seven biomaterials were acidified as follows: 50 mL of diluted sulfuric acid was applied to 100 g of fresh biomaterial (2:1 ratio, wv^{-1}) and the mixture was placed in an oven at 85 °C for 48 h. The sulfuric acid concentrations used were determined based on the results of Sica et al. (2023). For all the biomaterials, H_2SO_4 was applied in a concentration of 1.5 M (A1), a total of 73.5 g of H_2SO_4 per kg (fresh weight). For the three SSs, an additional treatment with 2.5 M H_2SO_4 was used (A2), with a total of 122.5 g of H_2SO_4 per kg (fresh weight). The amount of sulfuric acid applied per hectare for each treatment was calculated based on an application rate of 30 kg of total P per hectare, and the cost of sulfuric acid applied per hectare was based on March 2023 values from the US producer price index (Bureau of Labor Statistics): USD 218 per ton of sulfuric acid.

The water-extractable P (WEP) content was determined by shaking the biowastes on an end-over-end shaker for 1 h with deionized water at a ratio of 1:60. The samples were then filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter papers, and the ortho-P content in the extracts was analyzed by a flow-injection analyzer (FIAstar 5000, FOSS, Denmark) using ammonium molybdate. For the pH measurements, 2 g of biomaterial and 10 mL of deionized water were added to 15 mL centrifuge tubes and shaken on an end-over-end shaker for 1 h. Subsequently, the samples were allowed to stand for 1 h at room temperature before the pH was measured.

2.2. Pot experiment

2.2.1. Treatments

The treatments evaluated in this study were based on different methods of application of untreated and acidified biowastes. All biomaterials were applied untreated mixed with the soil to provide a well-defined homogeneous reference treatment (M) or placed in the soil close to the seeds (P). To assess the effects of acidification and increased P solubility, all biomaterials were acidified and placed close to the seeds (AP). An additional treatment aiming to induce acidification in the placement zone was added by co-applying the untreated biomaterials with ammonium sulfate (CL). The description of the treatments can be found in Table 2.

2.2.2. Setup

The soil used in this experiment was sampled at the University of Copenhagen's experimental farm in Taastrup (Denmark, 55°40'N, 12°16'E) from the unfertilized treatment (negative control) of the CRUCIAL long-term fertilization trial, which started in 2003 and was mainly cultivated with spring cereals. The soil was a low-P (WEP = 2 mg/kg) sandy loam (clay 12.6%, silt 14.3%, and sand 69.8%), classified as a Luvisol (FAO), previously described by Gómez-Muñoz et al. (2018). More detailed information on the CRUCIAL long-term trial and the soil used in this study can be found in Lemming et al. (2019) and López-Rayó et al. (2016). After collection, the soil was air-dried and sieved to 4 mm.

For each experimental unit, the equivalent of 1.875 kg of dried soil was filled into a plastic bag and topped up with pure and washed quartz sand of 0.4–0.8 mm grain size, in a 3:1 (soil-sand) ratio to give a total weight of 2.5 kg. Sand was added to increase the water infiltration rate and facilitate root growth throughout the experiment and to further decrease the amount of available P from the substrate. The soil-sand mixture (hereafter referred to as 'soil') was thoroughly homogenized in the plastic bags and liquid nutrient solution was applied to the dry soil to provide all the essential plant nutrients, except phosphorus, at the following rates (in mg per kg of soil): N = 150; K = 150; Ca = 40; Mg = 40; S = 20; Cu = 1.5; Zn = 1.2; Mo = 0.1; Fe = 3; B = 0.3; Mn = 3.

In the co-localized treatments (CL), the added volume of the nutrient solution was reduced to provide 135 mg of N kg⁻¹ (90% of the total N addition). The remaining 15 mg of N kg⁻¹ (10% of the total N addition) was co-applied with the biomaterials in the form of (NH₄)₂SO₄.

The soil bags were left open for 48 h at room temperature to allow the nutrient solutions to dry. The dried soil-nutrient mixture was homogenized by carefully mashing the areas where the nutrient solution was dried. Subsequently, the plastic bag was sealed and shaken by hand for one minute.

2.2.3. ³³P indirect soil labeling and P-fertilizers application

Deionized water was added to reach 40% of the water-holding capacity of the soil. The bags were sealed and left at room temperature for two weeks for pre-incubation to stimulate microbial activity, as described by Oehl et al. (2004). After that, a ³³P-orthophosphate solution was thoroughly mixed into each soil bag at a rate of 1 MBq per kg of dry soil. The soil bags were sealed and incubated for 14 days at room temperature.

The P fertilizers were applied at a rate of 60 mg of total P per kg of soil. For the acidified biomaterials, the total dry weight of the samples was measured before and after acidification. The increase in dry weight was considered as a dilution of total P and was taken into account when calculating the amount of P to be applied from the acidified biomaterial.

After incubation, for the mixed treatments, the P fertilizers were added to the bags, mixed, carefully transferred to the pots, and the mixture was packed to a bulk density of 1.25 g cm⁻³. For the placed treatments, the soil was portioned so that it could be added in three steps: 1) the pot was filled with soil to 5 cm below the top; 2) a 5 cm diameter tube was inserted into the pot, and soil was added to completely fill the pot; 3) the tube was removed, and the P fertilizer was placed in the remaining hole, which was then filled with the rest of the soil. For the co-localized treatments, the P fertilizers were mixed with NH₄SO₄ powder before being placed. For the placement, in all the steps the amount of soil was calculated and packed to a bulk density of 1.25 g cm⁻³.

2.2.4. Wheat sowing and growth conditions

Three winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* cv. Benchmark) seeds were sown in the center of each pot, 2 cm below the soil surface. Three days after emergence (DAE), the seedlings were thinned out, leaving one plant in each pot and ensuring that all plants were as similar as possible. The experiment was set up as a completely randomized design, with four replicates in each treatment. Every 2–3 days, the pots were randomly rotated and weighed to maintain the moisture content at 70% of the WHC. The climate chamber was set to a 16-

Table 2

Description of the treatments used in this study.

Abbreviation	Treatment	Application	Description	Biomaterial
M	untreated	mixed	The untreated biomaterial was applied mixed with the soil	All
P	untreated	placed	The untreated biomaterial was placed 3 cm below the seed	All
AP1	acidified	placed	The biomaterial was acidified with 1.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ (73.5 g H ₂ SO ₄ per kg of fresh weight) and was placed 3 cm below the seed	All
AP2	acidified	placed	The biomaterial was acidified with 2.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ (122.5 g H ₂ SO ₄ per kg of fresh weight) and was placed 3 cm below the seed	Only SS
CL	untreated	placed	The untreated biomaterial was co-applied localized with (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (15 mg of N per kg of soil) 3 cm below the seed	All

hour day cycle with a photon flux density of $600 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a constant temperature of 19°C . The night cycle was 8 h at a constant temperature of 15°C . The plants were harvested at 42 days after emergence (DAE).

After harvesting, soil samples were collected from the exact location where the biomaterials had been placed. For the mixed treatments, the soil samples were collected from a region corresponding to the placement location. The pH (H_2O , 1:5 soil:water ratio) of these soil samples was measured by shaking them for 1 h on an end-over-end shaker. The samples were then allowed to stand for 1 h at room temperature before the pH was measured.

2.2.5. Plant analyses

After harvest, the plant shoots were dried at 65°C for 48 h and the shoot dry matter was determined. The dried shoots were then ground to a fine powder and homogenized. A subsample was taken to determine the total N content in the shoots using an Elemental Analyzer (Vario macro cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Germany).

To determine the total P content of the seeds and shoots, subsamples of $100 \pm 10 \text{ mg}$ were ashed in small crucibles at 550°C for one hour. The ash was transferred to a 50-mL centrifuge tube, shaken on an end-over-end shaker for 16 h with 50 mL of $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and then filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter papers. The ortho-P content of the extract was determined using a flow-injection analyzer (FIAstar 5000, FOSS, Denmark). The extracts were mixed with a scintillation liquid (Ultima gold TM, Perkin Elmer) and analyzed for ^{33}P beta-emission using a liquid scintillation counter (Tri-Carb 2910TR, Perkin Elmer).

2.2.5.1. Estimation of Pdf seeds, Pdf soil, and Pdf fertilizer. The total P content in the shoots was divided into 3 pools: the Pdf (P derived from) seeds, the Pdf soil, and the Pdf fertilizer. To determine the Pdf seeds, the wheat seeds were weighed and only those with $55 \pm 5 \text{ mg}$ were selected for this experiment. The total P content in the seeds was determined to be $1.33 \text{ mg of P g}^{-1} \text{ seed}$. Thus, on average, each seed had a total P content of 0.072 mg . The contribution of seed P in the shoots was estimated to be 50% of the total seed P content (Mason et al., 2013), or $0.036 \text{ mg per plant}$. The seed contribution to the total plant P uptake was therefore assumed to be relatively low ($0.48 - 4.98\%$).

2.2.5.2. Calculations. The Pdf fertilizer in the plant was calculated using Eq. (1):

$$Pdf_{fert.} = \left(P_{UptPlant+P} - Pdf_{seedPlantP} - \left(\frac{TotalAct_{plant+P}}{TotalAct_{plantNoP}} \right) \right) \times (P_{UptPlantNoP} - Pdf_{seedPlantNoP}) \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), the $P_{UptPlant+P}$ is the P uptake by the plant fertilized with P, $Pdf_{seedPlant+P}$ is the Pdf seed of the plant fertilized with P, $TotalAct_{plant+P}$ is the total activity in the fertilized plant and $TotalAct_{plantNoP}$ is the total activity in the negative control plants, $P_{upt-PlantNoP}$ is the P uptake by the negative control plant, and $Pdf_{seedPlantNoP}$ is the Pdf seed in the negative control. More information on the calculations can be found in (Lemming et al., 2016; Nanzer et al., 2014).

The mineral phosphorus fertilizer equivalent (MFE) was calculated as the percentage that the Pdf fertilizer represented of the amount of P applied with the fertilizer (Eq. 2):

$$MFE \quad (\%) = 100 \times \frac{APR_{biomaterial}}{APR_{mineralP}} \quad (2)$$

Where, $APR_{biomaterial}$ is the apparent P recovery from the biomaterial and $APR_{mineralP}$ is the apparent P recovery from the mineral fertilizer (KH_2PO_4) applied mixed with the soil. APR was calculated as:

$$APR \quad (\%) = 100 \times \frac{P \text{ uptake biomaterial} - P \text{ uptake negative control}}{Total \text{ P applied}} \quad (3)$$

Re-analyzing some of the biomaterials revealed somewhat lower total P contents. Therefore, it cannot be excluded that the APR/MFE is underestimated in our study.

The nutrient indices of N, P, and S were calculated as in Eq. (4):

$$Nutrient \ index \quad (\%) = 100 \times \frac{Nutrient \ measured(g/kg)}{Nutrient \ critical \ content(g/kg)} \quad (4)$$

Where the nutrients measured are the N, P, and S contents in the plant shoots in this experiment.

The critical nitrogen contents were calculated according to Eq. (5) for wheat (Ziadi et al., 2010):

$$N(g/kg) = 3.85(\text{shoots dry matter, g})^{-0.57} \quad (5)$$

The critical P content was calculated according to Eq. (6) for wheat (Bélanger et al., 2015):

$$P(g/kg) = -0.677 + 0.221N \text{ measured} - 0.00292(N \text{ measured})^2 \quad (6)$$

The critical S content was calculated according to Eq. (7) for spring wheat (Reussi et al., 2012):

$$S(g/kg) = 0.37(\text{shoots dry matter, g})^{-0.169} \quad (7)$$

For the nutrient index values, 100 indicates an ideal situation, whereas a higher value indicates a luxurious consumption by the

crop and a value below 100 indicates a deficiency (Duru and Ducrocq, 1997).

2.3. Statistical analyses

The statistical analyses were performed to assess the effects of the treatments within each P fertilizer material, using IBM SPSS Statistics 27.0 to conduct a one-way ANOVA. Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$) was used to compare the means. For the shoot dry matter within the biomaterials, each treatment was compared to the negative control using Dunnett's test ($p < 0.05$). The homogeneity of variance of the data was confirmed using Levene's test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to check that the data followed a normal distribution. The graphs were generated using SigmaPlot version 14.0.

3. Results

3.1. Pre-treatment effects on pH of biomaterials

For both MBM I and MBM II, the acidification decreased the pH to 3.9 and increased the WEP to 82% and 69% of the total P, respectively. For the BGF I and BGF II, the pH was decreased to 1.6 and 3.5 and the WEP increased to 58% and 69% of the total P, respectively. For all the three acidified sewage sludges, the pH was below 2.0 and the WEP ranged from 13% to 50% of the total P (Table 3).

The amount of fresh biomaterial weight to be applied to supply 30 kg of P per hectare ranged from 758 kg for MBM I to 2915 kg for SS-Min. As a consequence, the amount of sulfuric acid to be applied per hectare due to the acidification also varied considerably between the biomaterials, with higher amounts for SS. In the case of MBM I, 55.7 kg of sulfuric acid would be applied per hectare, and 66.6 kg for BGF I (Table 3).

3.2. Fertilizer placement effects on shoot dry matter

The placement of acidified MBM II and BGF II (both pellets) gave similar or better biomass yields than the corresponding mixed and placed treatments. For MBM I, the placed acidified treatment produced more shoot biomass than the untreated placed material. For BGF I, there were no significant differences between the treatments. However, for the sewage sludge materials, placement benefited the untreated SS-Min, but acidification combined with placement of sewage sludge resulted in poor dry matter yields. The co-application of ammonium with MBM I, MBM II, and SS-B significantly reduced the shoot dry matter compared to the respective mixed treatments. For all biomaterials, the co-application with ammonium did not change or reduced (MBM) the shoot dry matter compared to the placement of untreated material (Fig. 1).

3.3. Fertilizer placement effects on P uptake and mineral fertilizer equivalent

The placement of untreated MBM I and MBM II significantly reduced the total P uptake and P derived from the fertilizer compared to the mixed and acidified placed treatments. For all other fertilizer treatments, except SS-V, the placement of the untreated material did not change P uptake or Pdf fertilizer compared to the untreated mixed treatment. For the MBM II, BGF I, and BGF II, the acidified

Table 3

pH, water-extractable P, total fresh weight of biomaterial application per hectare, amount of sulfuric acid added per hectare, and extras costs associated with sulfuric acid addition for all the biomaterials and treatments assessed in this study. BGF = biogas fiber; MBM = meat and bone meal; SS = sewage sludge. U = untreated; A1 = acidified with 1.5 M H₂SO₄; A2 = acidified with 2.5 M H₂SO₄.

			BGF I	BGF II	MBM I	MBM II	SS-B	SS-V	SS-Min
pH		U	9.1	8.2	5.8	5.9	8.8	8.8	7.9
	(H ₂ O, 1:5)	A1	1.6	3.5	3.9	3.9	1.9	1.9	1.4
		A2	-	-	-	-	1.5	1.5	1.2
WEP*	g kg ⁻¹ (% of total P)	U	4.54 (14%)	0.1 (0.1%)	0.89 (2.2%)	0.1 (0.02%)	0.38 (0.9%)	0.23 (0.6%)	0.59 (1.7%)
		A1	19.1 (58%)	8.3 (69%)	32.3 (82%)	23.4 (64%)	7.3 (18%)	5.1 (13%)	12.1 (35%)
		A2	-	-	-	-	14.1 (34%)	12.4 (31%)	17.0 (50%)
Biomaterial application* *	kg per hectare (fresh weight)		906	2500	758	824	2409	2487	2915
Sulfuric acid application* *	kg per hectare	A1	66.6	183	55.7	60.6	177	182	214
		A2	-	-	-	-	295	305	357
Sulfuric acid extra costs* **	USD per hectare	A1	14.5	39.9	12.1	13.2	38.6	39.7	46.7
		A2	-	-	-	-	64.3	66.5	77.8

*the WEP as % of the total P is provided in parentheses.

**Considering an application rate of 30 kg of total P per hectare, based on Danish phosphorus application limits.

***Based on US producer price index (Bureau of Labor Statistics): USD 218 per ton of sulfuric acid in March 2023.

Fig. 1. Shoot dry matter of wheat fertilized with MBM (i), MBM pellets (ii), BGF (iii), BGF pellets (iv), SS-B (v), SS-V (vi), SS-Min (vii), and mineral fertilizers (viii), applied untreated and mixed with the soil (M), untreated and placed 3 cm below the seed (P), acidified with 1.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (AP1), acidified with 2.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (AP2, treatment applied only to the sewage sludge materials), and placed 3 cm below the seed, co-applied with an ammonium source (CL). Two mineral P fertilizers (Min and Dc) were applied mixed (M) with the soil and placed (P) 3 cm below the seeds. For each material, different lowercase letters indicate a significant difference between treatments (Tukey's HSD test, $p < 0.05$). Asterisks indicate that the treatment was significantly greater than the negative control (no P fertilizer applied, Dunnett's test, $p < 0.05$), which is represented by the reference line in each graph. Error bars represent the standard error of each treatment ($n = 4$).

(caption on next page)

Fig. 2. P uptake from the soil and the fertilizer of wheat fertilized with MBM (i), MBM pellets (ii), BGF (iii), BGF pellets (iv), SS-B (v), SS-V (vi), SS-Min (vii), and mineral fertilizers (viii) applied untreated and mixed with the soil (M), untreated and placed 3 cm below the seed (P), acidified with 1.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (AP1), acidified with 2.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (AP2, treatment applied only to the sewage sludge materials), and placed 3 cm below the seed, co-applied with an ammonium source (CL). Two mineral P fertilizers (Min and Dc) were applied mixed (M) with the soil and placed (P) 3 cm below the seeds. Within each material tested, different uppercase letters indicate a significant difference in the total P uptake. Different lowercase black letters indicate a significant difference in the P uptake from the fertilizer whereas different white lowercase letters indicate a significant difference in the P uptake from the soil.

Fig. 3. Mineral fertilizer equivalent (%) of wheat fertilized with MBM (i), MBM pellets (ii), BGF (iii), BGF pellets (iv), SS-B (v), SS-V (vi), SS-Min (vii), and mineral fertilizers (viii), applied untreated and mixed with the soil (M), untreated and placed 3 cm below the seed (P), acidified with 1.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (AP1), acidified with 2.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (AP2, treatment applied only to the sewage sludge), and placed 3 cm below the seed co-applied with an ammonium source (CL). Two mineral P fertilizers (Min and Dc) were applied mixed (M) with the soil and placed (P) 3 cm below the seeds. For each material, different lowercase letters indicate a significant difference between treatments (Tukey's HSD test, $p < 0.05$). Error bars represent the standard error of each treatment ($n = 4$).

placed treatment had a significantly higher total P uptake and P derived from the fertilizer compared to the corresponding untreated mixed treatment. For all three SSs, the total P uptake and P derived from the fertilizers were significantly lower in the acidified placed treatments than in the untreated mixed and placed treatments. For the SS-Min, the co-application with ammonium sulfate showed the highest total P uptake and P derived from the fertilizer (Fig. 2).

When assessing the untreated materials, the MBM I had a comparable MFE to the mineral P fertilizers when mixed with the soil. The placement of acidified materials resulted in high MFEs compared to the placement of untreated materials and in the case of MBM I and BGF I, these values were above 100% (Fig. 3).

The co-localization of ammonium and SS-min resulted in the highest total P uptake and P derived from the fertilizer compared to all other treatments. For the SS-B, the co-localization with ammonium significantly increased the P derived from the fertilizer. For all other biomaterials, the co-localization with ammonium did not change or reduced total P uptake and P derived from the fertilizer (Fig. 2).

The placement of MBM II, acidified BGF II, SS-B, and SS-V significantly reduced the P uptake from the soil compared to the mixed treatments. For all biomaterials co-applied with ammonium (except MBM I and SS-V), the P uptake from the soil was significantly lower than in the untreated mixed treatment (Fig. 2).

3.4. Nutrient indices

The placement of untreated MBM I, MBM II and acidified SS resulted in critically low phosphorus nutrient indices (<60%), indicating P deficiency. The placement of acidified BGF I and BGF II significantly increased the PNI compared to the untreated mixed treatment. The nitrogen nutrient index (NNI) was above 100% in most of the treatments, except for the acidified SSs, MBM II placed and co-applied with ammonium sulfate, and the mineral fertilizer mixed into the soil. The placement of MBM II also significantly reduced the sulfur nutrient index (SNI), and for all biomaterials co-applied with ammonium sulfate, the SNI was below 100% (Table 4).

Table 4

Phosphorus nutrient index (PNI), nitrogen nutrient index (NNI) and sulfur nutrient index (SNI) of the seven biomaterials, applied untreated and mixed with the soil (M), untreated and placed 3 cm below the seed (P), acidified with 1.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (A1), acidified with 2.5 M H₂SO₄ and placed 3 cm below the seed (A2, treatment applied only to the sewage sludge), placed 3 cm below the seed co-applied with an ammonium source (CL), and of the negative control (0 P, no P fertilizer applied) and two mineral P fertilizers (Min and Dc) that were applied mixed (M) with the soil and placed (P) 3 cm below the seed.

Biomaterial:		M	P	AP1	AP2	CL
MBM I	PNI (%)	73.9 ± 4 a	56.9 ± 8 b	85.1 ± 13 a	-	56.6 ± 5 b
	NNI (%)	113 ± 11	132 ± 5	136 ± 8	-	108 ± 13
	SNI (%)	121 ± 11 a	103 ± 6 a	102 ± 4 a	-	79.2 ± 3.5 b
	Soil pH	6.78 ± 0.07 a	6.32 ± 0.14 b	5.45 ± 0.04c	-	6.21 ± 0.11 b
MBM II	PNI (%)	74.7 ± 10 b	50.3 ± 1.6c	103 ± 11 a	-	67.8 ± 12 b
	NNI (%)	128 ± 9 ab	83.3 ± 5 b	133 ± 4 a	-	90.9 ± 13 ab
	SNI (%)	102 ± 3 a	80.7 ± 5 b	97.6 ± 3 a	-	78.4 ± 3.6 b
	Soil pH	6.57 ± 0.15 a	6.55 ± 0.11 a	5.25 ± 0.14c	-	6.15 ± 0.05 b
BGF I	PNI (%)	56.4 ± 5 b	89.5 ± 10 ab	112 ± 12 a	-	98.0 ± 17 ab
	NNI (%)	125 ± 7	127 ± 3	125 ± 8	-	103 ± 12
	SNI (%)	93.1 ± 5 ab	100 ± 4 a	100 ± 4 a	-	86.3 ± 7 b
	Soil pH	6.85 ± 0.07 b	7.45 ± 0.08 a	3.69 ± 0.14 d	-	6.01 ± 0.05c
BGF II	PNI (%)	80.8 ± 11 b	78.0 ± 3 b	98.9 ± 10 a	-	80.3 ± 3 b
	NNI (%)	126 ± 7 ab	111 ± 6 b	155 ± 9 a	-	109 ± 5 b
	SNI (%)	98.3 ± 5 ab	94.2 ± 6 ab	105 ± 7 a	-	86 ± 7 b
	Soil pH	6.98 ± 0.08 a	7.15 ± 0.02 a	3.35 ± 0.08c	-	5.25 ± 0.25 b
SS-B	PNI (%)	65.4 ± 8c	82.8 ± 5 b	56.6 ± 5c	50.6 ± 4c	112 ± 11 a
	NNI (%)	149 ± 13 a	106 ± 6 b	86.8 ± 4c	107 ± 5 b	112 ± 10 b
	SNI (%)	117 ± 12 a	90.6 ± 3 b	89.2 ± 4 b	94.9 ± 7 ab	85.9 ± 6 b
	Soil pH	7.06 ± 0.05 b	7.57 ± 0.11 a	2.91 ± 0.22 d	2.57 ± 0.14 d	6.33 ± 0.11c
SS-V	PNI (%)	78.2 ± 17 a	60.0 ± 13 ab	58.1 ± 1.1 ab	52.5 ± 4 b	76.3 ± 9 a
	NNI (%)	104 ± 9 ab	128 ± 9 a	90.9 ± 1.7 b	91.5 ± 7 b	118 ± 6 ab
	SNI (%)	95.6 ± 3 a	92.3 ± 4 a	92.6 ± 4 a	77.9 ± 5 b	92.6 ± 3 a
	Soil pH	7.16 ± 0.12 b	7.92 ± 0.21 a	2.82 ± 0.12 d	2.45 ± 0.25 d	5.81 ± 0.19c
SS-Min	PNI (%)	80.5 ± 8 b	70.9 ± 8 b	48.4 ± 2c	52.3 ± 5c	114 ± 23 a
	NNI (%)	91.5 ± 4 b	115.8 ± 10 a	83 ± 6 b	79 ± 10 b	116 ± 13 a
	SNI (%)	84.3 ± 7 ab	95.2 ± 4 a	76.5 ± 5 b	73.2 ± 3 ab	94.0 ± 9 a
	Soil pH	6.89 ± 0.07 a	7.02 ± 0.12 a	2.52 ± 0.17c	2.05 ± 0.07c	5.42 ± 0.31c
Mineral fertilizers	0 P		MinM	MinP	DcM	DcP
	PNI (%)	47.4 ± 5c	97.8 ± 13 ab	122 ± 16 a	103 ± 15 ab	122 ± 10 a
	NNI (%)	55.3 ± 4 c	83.2 ± 1.5 b	90.6 ± 4 ab	101 ± 12 a	101 ± 9 a
	SNI (%)	74.7 ± 3 b	88.9 ± 6 ab	93.4 ± 5 ab	103 ± 10 a	98.6 ± 13 a

BGF = biogas fiber; MBM = meat and bone meal; SS = sewage sludge.

Different lowercase letters indicate a significant difference (Tukey HSD, p < 0.05) between treatments within the same biomaterial. Values after ± indicate the standard errors (n = 4).

3.5. pH in the placement zone

The treatments showed a significant effect on soil pH. For all the biomaterials, the acidification resulted in a significant reduction of the pH in the placement area after wheat cultivation compared to the M, P, and CL treatments. The CL treatments for the BGF, BGF pellets, and all the three SSs had significantly lower pH values than the M and P treatments (Table 4).

4. Discussion

4.1. Effects of acidification on biowaste P solubility

The meat and bone meal is mainly composed of Ca-bound P (Jeng et al., 2007), whereas the solid fraction of digestate also contains Mg-bound P as well as vivianite ($(\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 - (\text{H}_2\text{O})_8)$) (Möller and Müller, 2012). As shown by Sica et al. (2023) and Regueiro et al. (2020), the acidification of MBM and BGF to a pH below 4 can dissolve most of the P and increase the water-extractable P in soils and the P availability, which was confirmed in the present study.

The $(\text{Al} + \text{Fe})/\text{P}$ molar ratio is negatively correlated with the P availability of biowastes (Ylivainio et al., 2021). In the case of sewage sludge, the aluminum and iron salts used in wastewater treatment plants lead to the formation of Fe- and Al-bound P, reducing P availability. For this reason, sewage sludge also required high amounts of acid to dissolve most of its P (Table 3). To completely dissolve Al- and Fe-bound P in sewage sludge, a pH below 2 is required (Xu et al., 2015). However, the acidification of sewage sludge can also solubilize harmful metals, such as aluminum, iron, and heavy metals (Keskinen et al., 2023).

4.2. Effects of application method and acidification on P availability

4.2.1. Untreated materials mixed into soil

In pot and/or rhizobox studies, such as the one conducted in this study, biomaterials are often “homogeneously mixed into the entire soil volume”, which was sieved prior to experiments (Lemming et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2016). This does not represent the reality of field conditions, where the distribution of fertilizers (especially biomaterials) is heterogeneous and susceptible to concentrate preferential flow patterns throughout the soil profile (Petersen et al., 2001), creating nutrient-rich zones in the soil (Hodge, 2004) and limiting the contact between soil and fertilizers to discrete bands or patches (Magid et al., 2006). Thus, we believe that the mixed treatments used in this study represent artificial conditions that will tend to overestimate the potential P uptake under field conditions.

For both BGF, MBM II and all three SSs untreated mixed, the mineral fertilizer equivalent value was between 40% and 70%, which is consistent with previous studies (Möller et al., 2018; Möller and Müller, 2012; Regueiro et al., 2020). However, for MBM I, the MFE was around 100%. In a couple of studies, Brod et al. (2015a), (2015b) found that the application of meat and bone meal mixed with acidic soils tended to increase the P use efficiency compared to alkaline soils. They suggested that at lower pH, the Ca-bound P in meat and bone meal can be dissolved and become available to the plant. However, in this study, we used a soil with a neutral pH (6.8). Also, MBM I and MBM II had the same origin, the main difference being that the first was in powder form, whereas the second was pelleted. We speculate that the high content of nitrogen in MBM may have stimulated plant growth in the early stages, thereby increasing the P uptake, which is also in accordance with the NNI. The physical form of the fertilizer can have a large influence on its P availability (Rodrigues et al., 2021), which can be increased with smaller particle sizes (Müller-Stöver et al., 2021).

4.2.2. Placement: untreated vs. acidified

Christiansen et al. (2020) assessed the plant P uptake of several biomaterials in three different soils, including meat and bone meal collected from the same company as the MBM I and MBM II used in this study, and found a very low P use efficiency of meat and bone meal applied in a layer, even though they used three acidic soils (pH values: 5.1, 5.2, 5.3). In this study, the P derived from the fertilizer was close to zero in the untreated placed treatment. Both MBM I and MBM II contained about 10% of nitrogen, mainly in organic form, and when applied to the soil, this N is expected to be mineralized, significantly increasing the NH_4^+ content in the placement zone and its surroundings (Chaves et al., 2006; Mondini et al., 2008). In another study, by Pan et al. (2016) observed that when chicken manure was applied localized, faba bean root development was inhibited up to 5 cm from the placement area due to the formation of an NH_4^+ toxicity zone around the biomaterial layer. Therefore, we speculate that the placement zone and surrounding soil of the untreated MBM created a toxicity zone that inhibited root growth and prevented the plant from accessing fertilizer P.

In contrast, the placement of both acidified MBMs significantly increased the total P uptake compared to the untreated placed for MBM I and compared to all treatments for MBM II. A plausible explanation could be that acidification reduces the pH of the placement zone to below 5.5, thereby inhibiting N mineralization (Pietri and Brookes, 2008) and reducing ammonium toxicity. However, Sica et al. (2023) found that the placement of acidified meat and bone meal increased the pH of the placement zone and the surrounding soil after only 2 days. In fact, the results of Zireeni et al. (2023) demonstrated that the application of acidified biowastes increased the N mineralization to NH_4^+ . Thus, we speculate that the acidification increased the amount of P released to the soil and the P diffusion rates, thereby increasing the available P levels outside the toxicity zone, allowing the roots to access P from the fertilizer.

BGF I showed a significantly higher total P uptake and P derived from fertilizer in the AP1 treatment compared to the untreated mixed treatment and a MFE of around 120%. Pedersen et al. (2017) assessed the effect of different degrees of acidification of cattle slurry and application methods on P use efficiency and found that the P uptake in early-stage maize was significantly increased when strongly acidified slurry was applied in narrow bands. Regueiro et al. (2020) found that acidification of the solid fraction of digestate significantly increased the P uptake by maize at 30 days after emergence. However, they did not find a significant difference in terms of

shoot dry matter. This is consistent with the findings of our study, where the acidification did not result in significant differences in shoot dry matter. Previous studies by [Romer and Schilling \(1986\)](#) suggested that wheat plants take up a significant proportion of their total P content before substantial shoot growth occurs. This may indicate that the untreated mixed BGF treatment had a latent P deficiency ([Frydenvang et al., 2015](#)) at 42 DAE, without showing symptoms or a significant reduction in shoot dry matter during the period of this experiment.

At pH levels below 4.5, root growth is negatively affected, and this is exacerbated in the range of 3.5 to 4.0 ([Yan et al., 1992](#)). Interestingly, although BGF I and BGF II had significantly higher P uptake from the fertilizer, the pH values in the placement zone were still acidic - 3.69 and 3.35, respectively - at 42 DAE. [Sica et al. \(2023\)](#) showed that already after 12 days, the placement of the acidified solid fraction of biogas digestate released about 77% of the total P applied. This could indicate that for these biomaterials, the acidification increased the P availability not only in the placement zone but also further out due to diffusion into a larger surrounding soil space.

Our results are consistent with previous findings by [Wang et al. \(2016\)](#), who showed that placement of sewage sludge did not increase wheat shoot dry matter or total P uptake. [Lemming et al. \(2016\)](#) also observed similar results in maize: although a placed application of sewage sludge increased root density in the sludge patch, it reduced P uptake from the soil, suggesting a trade-off for root exploration of other soil resources. In our study, we found that the placement of SS-B significantly reduced NNI, SNI, and P derived from the soil compared to the mixed treatment, indicating limited acquisition of nitrogen, sulfur, and phosphorus from the bulk soil. This indeed suggests that the placement of untreated SS may imply an opportunity cost for the plant between exploring the P available in the placement zone and other soil resources.

[Keskinen et al. \(2023\)](#) found that acidification of sewage sludge can increase the P solubility and availability. However, in our study, despite an increase in water-extractable P, the SS acidification treatments had a negative effect on total P uptake, P derived from the soil, and P derived from the fertilizer. Plant growth was also adversely affected and did not significantly differ from the negative control. [Keskinen et al. \(2023\)](#) acidified the sewage sludge to a pH of 4.5 and applied it mixed to the soil. In our study, all three SSs had a relatively high content of aluminum, which can be dissolved at a pH below 2 ([Xu et al., 2015](#)). Therefore, when placed close to the seeds, the acidified SSs may have created an Al toxicity zone that inhibited root development, reduced the access to the P fertilizer and consequently the plant growth ([Delhaize et al., 1993](#); [Siecińska et al., 2019](#)).

4.2.3. Co-application with ammonium sulfate

The co-application of biowastes with nitrogen can acidify the soil and increase P solubility ([Amin, 2023](#)). Among ammonium salts, ammonium sulfate is the one with the highest acidification potential ([Chien et al., 2008](#)). In this study, the co-application of ammonium sulfate with meat and bone meal did not result in a significant difference in terms of P uptake compared to the untreated placed (P) treatment. We speculate that for MBM, the nitrogen mineralization rates were high, supplying large amounts of ammonium to the soil, which masked the effects of the ammonium sulfate.

[Wang et al. \(2016\)](#) found that the localized co-application of sewage sludge with an ammonium source reduced pH and increased P availability in the placement area, but also inhibited plant shoot and root growth due to ammonium toxicity. In our study, we applied lower amounts of ammonium salt but still observed a significant pH reduction in the placement area, which may be the reason for the increased P availability and uptake from the fertilizer for SS-B, SS-V, and SS-Min compared to the untreated placed treatments.

4.3. Practical implications

4.3.1. Use of sulfuric acid and potential alternatives

In Denmark, the use of sulfuric acid for acidification of animal slurry and digestate has been studied and implemented since the early 2000 s to reduce ammonia emissions ([Fangueiro et al., 2015b](#)). This treatment has also shown potential to increase the solubility and availability of phosphorus in animal-derived biowastes ([Regueiro et al., 2020](#)). In addition, [Eriksen et al. \(2008\)](#) reported a significantly higher sulfur fertilizer value in slurry acidified with sulfuric acid, with the sulfate content remaining stable and plant available even after 11 months of storage. However, further research is needed to understand the fate of S when acidified biomaterials are localized in the soil.

Alternative acidifying agents, such as citric acid ([Mihoub et al., 2022](#)) and other organic acids, have been studied as potential replacements for sulfuric acid; however, they have not shown promising results ([Regueiro et al., 2016](#)). In fact, a report from the Research Institute of Sweden (RISE) suggests that two to three times more organic acids would be needed to achieve similar results as sulfuric acid, resulting in a 10 times higher cost ([Joubin et al., 2018](#)). [Garder et al. \(2023\)](#) demonstrated that bioacidification could reduce the amount of sulfuric acid required for slurry acidification, but it also significantly reduced the fertilizer value of the slurry, possibly due to increased nutrient immobilization. In this study, the co-application with MBM and BGF did not show significant differences compared to the untreated placed biomaterial. However, for all the three SS, co-application significantly increased the P uptake from the fertilizer compared to the respective untreated placed treatments, indicating that this could be a potential approach to acidify the rhizosphere and increase the P fertilizer value of sewage sludge.

4.3.2. Applicability

[Sica et al. \(2023\)](#) have shown that higher amounts of sulfuric acid are required to solubilize phosphorus from sewage sludge compared to meat and bone meal and the solid fraction of digestate. Strong acidification of sewage sludge solubilizes not only phosphorus but also other metals such as aluminum, iron, and heavy metals ([Korving et al., 2018](#)), which probably inhibited plant growth when acidified sewage sludge was applied directly below the seeds in our study. In addition, the higher acidification

requirement of sewage sludge resulted in impractical amounts of sulfuric acid being applied (177 to 357 kg per hectare), leading to significant costs (38.6 to 77.8 USD per hectare), indicating that this approach may not be feasible for this type of biowaste.

On the other hand, BGF and MBM (except BGF II) required lower quantities of sulfuric acid to be applied, resulting in costs ranging from 12.1 to 14.5 USD per hectare. The main difference between BGF I and BGF II is the use of centrifuge decanting separation in BGF I, which improves separation efficiency and phosphorus recovery, leading to higher phosphorus contents (Chuda et al., 2021) and reduced sulfuric acid requirements. Overall, the acidification of these biomaterials showed promising results compared to the treatment where the untreated material was applied localized. However, to develop a phosphorus-efficient biobased fertilizer with reduced costs, further studies are required to explore methods to minimize the amount of sulfuric acid applied. Additionally, our results revealed that the placement of acidified MBM II, BGF I, and BGF II increased the phosphorus uptake from the fertilizer by 2–3 times. Therefore, it is worth investigating the possibility of reducing the phosphorus application rate due to the significant improvements in phosphorus use efficiency observed.

4.3.3. Potential human health and environmental risks

The acidification of biomaterials has potential drawbacks in terms of human health and environmental risks, as it may increase the bioavailability of heavy metals and the movement of phosphorus in the soil. With regard to the first concern, both MBM and BGF were more than 10 times below the heavy metal content limits established by the Danish executive order for the agricultural use of waste (except for Cd, which was not detected) (Table 1).

Regarding the second issue, Sica et al. (2023) observed that acidification increased the release of phosphorus from the biomaterials to the soil. However, after 12 days, the movement of phosphorus was limited to a few millimeters in the soil, indicating lower diffusion compared to mineral phosphorus fertilizers (Rech et al., 2018). Additionally, Li et al. (2019) showed that acidification had no significant effect on phosphorus movement in the soil or on phosphorus concentration in soil leachates. These findings suggest that the acidification process does not pose significant risks in terms of phosphorus dispersion in the environment or potential contamination of soil leachates. However, further studies are needed to investigate the effects of acidification on heavy metal uptake and on the food quality for animal and human consumption and on the movement of P in the soil and potential environmental risks.

5. Conclusions

The placement of untreated biomaterial generally did not increase plant growth and P uptake under the experimental conditions used. The placement of acidified materials showed positive effects on plant phosphorus uptake for MBM and BGF. Conversely, acidification of all three sewage sludge samples significantly inhibited plant growth and phosphorus uptake. We believe that these results may have significant implications for the development of effective biobased phosphorus fertilizers from meat and bone meal and the solid fraction of biogas digestate that can efficiently replace mineral P fertilizers. However, further studies are needed to assess the applicability, economic viability, and potential environmental and human health risks associated with the use of sulfuric acid as acidifying agent.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Pietro Sica: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. Clara Kopp: Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. Jakob Magid: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration. Dorette Muller-Stover: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

The raw data of the experiments performed in this study are openly available online at the Electronic Research Data Archive (ERDA) from the University of Copenhagen: <https://doi.org/10.17894/ucph.65efb24c-8d79-4f92-b430-0f178de11e05>

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